

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF FIBER METAL LAMINATE JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber metal laminate is hybrid composites formed to optimize the properties of metal and fiber reinforced laminae for weight saving and better mechanical properties. This paper aims to study the failure strength and failure mode of FML in single-bolted single-lapped joint. The single-bolted single-lapped joints of FML and monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy were investigated. The failure mode, load-displacement curves and bearing stress-strain curves of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint and FML joint were measured and studied. The results show that the bearing and shear-out failure are the damage modes of FML joint. The fracture occurs mainly around the bolt hole in FML joint. The ultimate load of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum joint is 2.4 times higher than that of FML joint. When the bearing strain is more than 10%, the bearing stress of the FML joint is hardly increased.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber metal laminate (FML) is a family of hybrid laminates that was developed at Delft University of Technology[1]. FML was composed by aluminum alloy sheet layers and fiber reinforced composite layers. FML has many excellent mechanical properties such as outstanding fatigue resistance, good blunt notch strength and better bearing strength, which has been proved by successfully applying in A380[2, 3]. Because of the advantages of inspection and replacement, the mechanically fastened joints are applied in aircraft structures[4]. The mechanical fastened joint is the primary means for transferring load in aircraft structures.

The bolted joints of hybrid laminates with the metal layer were investigated to assure the failure mode and failure strength. Zu [4] investigated the tightening torque in fiber metal laminate joint. The results show that the maximum of ultimate failure load was obtained when the tightening torque was 10N·m. Reiner [5] investigated the failure modes in hybrid titanium composites laminates and found that debonding between the titanium sheet and the fiber-reinforced polymer laminate is the major failure mode. Meola [6] investigated the effect of the width W , the hole diameter D and the distance of the hole from the edge E to assure strength and behavior in FML joint. The edge distance to hole diameter ratio (E/D) and width to hole diameter ratio (W/D) are the important factors to determine different strengths and failure modes. The bearing strength of FML decreases with the growth of the value of parameter[7]. Due to the weak interlaminar strength in FML, delamination is the dominant failure mode[8-10]. Wang [11] found that lateral constraint could increase the bearing strength by more than 20% since it restrains delamination growth. The effects of secondary bending stresses and the load redistribution in FML joints on the failure mode are widely studied. The load redistribution between intact fastener rows and the

cracked fastener row accelerates crack growth with crack length[10]. Slagter[12] investigated the pin and bolt bearing behavior of two FML types for testing configurations and geometries.

Despite lots of work concerning the mechanical properties of FML joints have been done, their properties still need more understanding and attention. The failure mode and failure strength of FML joint will be the research emphases. In this study, the failure mode, load-displacement curves and bearing stress-strain curves of AL 2024-T3 joint and FML joint were measured and examined. Experiments of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminium joint and FML joint were applied to assess the failure mode and failure strength.

2 EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Experiment configuration

In this study, FML has been fabricated from three layers of 2024-T3 aluminium alloy plates and two layers of S2-glass fiber layer with lay-up $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$. The configuration, geometry and stacking sequence of the specimens is illustrated in Figure 1. The FML is made of aluminum layer with the thickness of 0.254mm and fiber layer with the thickness of 0.15mm. The 0° fiber direction is the direction of rolling the aluminum layer. The monolithic 2024-T3 aluminium alloy joints were also measured. The monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy thickness is 2mm. The specimens of the two materials have the same plane size (135mm×36mm) and the diameter of the hole is 4 mm. To avoid eccentricity of loading path, the length of the shim is 50mm. To avoid eccentricity of loading path, the length of the shim is 50mm.

Figure 1 Specimens configuration. (a) Configuration and geometry; (b)The stacking sequence of FML.

2.2 Experimental setup and procedures

In this work, the single-bolted single-lapped joints of FML were studied. The experiments have been carried out using DDL100 electronic universal testing machine as shown in Figure 2 (a). According to standard ASTM D5961[13] which is the standard test method to determine bearing strength of polymer matrix composite laminates, all the specimens of FML joints and aluminum alloy joints were loaded to failure under uniaxial tension with the speed of 2 mm/min. The curves of load vs time were obtained and displayed by the test machine. In order to offset the eccentric nature of single-lapped joints, the clamp was designed to fix specimen during the loading process.

The strain gauges were set to measure the strain around the joint on the specimens as shown in Figure 2 (b). The strain test points on specimen have 18 measuring points including 12 strain gauge on

the symmetrical position of 40mm from the hole and 6 strain gauge on the around the hole. The strain gauge test points are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Experimental setup for the quasi-static loading experiments. (a)DDL100 electronic universal testing machine; (b)strain gauge of the front side in specimens; (c)strain gauge of the back side in specimens.

Figure 3 The strain gauge test points on the specimens. (a) In front of specimens; (b) In back of specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Failure mode of two joints

The failure modes of the single-bolted single-lapped joint of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy and FML after the loading were analyzed and shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Net tension and bearing are the main failure mode of the monolithic aluminum alloy joints. As is shown in Figure 4 (c), the secondary bending caused by the rotational motion of bolt may lead to the out-of-plane displacement of around hole. Therefore, the monolithic aluminum alloy joint was not only in-plane failure but also an out-of-plane displacement. However, the rotational motion of bolt is not lead to obviously out-of-plane displacement in the single-lapped FML joints. Bearing and shear-out are the main failure mode of FML joints shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4 The failure modes of single-bolted single-lapped joint of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy. (a) The front view; (b)The back view; (c)The side view

Figure 5 The failure modes of single-bolted single-lapped joint of FML. (a) The front view; (b)The back view; (c)The side view

3.2 Load-displacement curves

Figure 6 shows the load-displacement data for the aluminum alloy joint and FML joint. Ultimate load and ultimate failure displacement of different specimens are shown in Table 1. The ultimate load of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint is about 12kN. However, the ultimate load of FML joint drops to about 5 kN. The ultimate load of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint is 2.4 times higher than that FML joint. A load of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint and FML joint first steady increases with the rise of displacement. When the load is ultimate load, the drop of load in FML joint is slower than monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint. This is because of the effect of fiber bridging in FML.

Figure 6 Load-displacement curves. (a) The monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joints; (b)FML joints.

Joint	Sample number	Ultimate load (kN)	Ultimate failure displacement (mm)
2024-T3 aluminum alloy joints	1	12.1017	8.0038
	2	11.7650	5.9862
	3	11.1879	7.0075
FML joints	1	5.2837	5.0183
	2	5.3187	4.4889
	3	5.2837	4.9988

Table 1 Ultimate mechanical properties of between 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joints and FML joints.

3.3 Bearing stress-strain curves

The bearing stress-strain curves for the aluminum alloy joint and the FML joint are shown in Figure 7. When bearing the strain is less than 5%, the bearing stress-strain curves of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint and FML joint is similar while bearing stress increasing rapidly. When the bearing strain is less than 10% and over 5%, the slope of the bearing stress-strain curves of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint and FML joint descended. The slope of the bearing stress-strain curves of FML joint is lower than monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint.

Figure 7 Bearing stress-strain curves

When the bearing strain is more than 10%, the bearing stress of the aluminum alloy joint is slowly increased and the bearing stress-strain curve of FML joint becomes flat. This is because that ultimate strength of FML joint possessed a smaller than the aluminum alloy joint. When the bearing strain is more than 10%, the strength of FML joint is failure strength.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presented the failure mode, load-displacement curves and bearing stress-strain curves of 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joints and FML joints. The main results were summarized as follows:

- (1) Experimental results show that the failure modes are bearing and shear-out on the FML joint. Net tension and bearing are the failure mode of the aluminum alloy joint.
- (2) The monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint was not only in-plane failure but also out-of-plane displacement around hole. FML joint was not obviously out-of-plane displacement.
- (3) The ultimate load of monolithic 2024-T3 aluminum alloy joint is about 2.4 times higher than FML joint.
- (4) The bearing stress of FML joint is almost invariant when the bearing strain is more than 10%.

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